

Empowering Innovation: How Knowledge Management Infrastructure Drives Progress in Iraq's Pharmaceutical Industry

Heba Raheem Ataa
Sunni Endowment, Iraq

Qasim Ali Jassim
Sunni Endowment, Iraq

Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to establish the relationship between knowledge management infrastructure and organisational innovation in the Iraqi pharmaceutical industry. To achieve this objective, it is essential to diagnose the issues related to knowledge management infrastructure and organisational innovation in the study area. Understanding these issues required field visits to several specialised pharmaceutical companies. A Likert scale questionnaire was developed and administered to a sample of 390 employees from several pharmaceutical companies. After data collection, it was processed using statistical tools (SPSS, Amos) and a descriptive-analytical methodology, which informed the interpretation of the results. The results indicated a significant influence of knowledge management infrastructure across all dimensions on organisational innovation in the Iraqi pharmaceutical sector. In light of these findings, several suggestions have been made, the most important of which include increasing organisational creativity by improving information sharing, investing in technology, and reforming organisational policies to foster a more inventive atmosphere.

Keywords: *Knowledge Management Infrastructure, Organizational Innovation, Iraqi Pharmaceutical Industry.*

JEL Classification codes: *O32, M11.*

Suggested citation: Ataa, H.R., & Jassim, Q.A. (2025). Empowering Innovation: How Knowledge Management Infrastructure Drives Progress in Iraq's Pharmaceutical Industry. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(2), 133-143. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2025.2(2).13

Introduction

Infrastructure is the lifeline of any activity in general, and knowledge management activities in particular, as it plays a crucial role in improving efficiency. Relevant studies and literature have emphasised the importance of a robust infrastructure to support the development of successful knowledge management. This is achieved by integrating knowledge management skills with technological support capabilities, in addition to establishing an advanced technological infrastructure that includes sophisticated databases and an extensive knowledge repository. Furthermore, it is essential to foster an organisational culture that supports knowledge management mechanisms within the institution (Al-Bataniya & Al-Zoubi, 2016).

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Organisational innovation is closely linked to entrepreneurship, as it is associated with the strategy of developing, proposing, adopting or implementing a new idea, whether it is related to behaviour, processes, products, policies, practices, programmes or services, either implicitly generated or explicitly implemented. This makes organisational innovation a fundamental measure of the entrepreneurial production characteristics that organisational members strive to achieve (Soomro et al., 2021).

From this perspective, organisational innovation plays a crucial role in enabling organisations to gain a competitive advantage over their rivals in both local and international markets. This competitive advantage ultimately contributes to increasing the economic returns to society. Achieving such superiority requires organisations to operate flexibly in dynamic environments, enabling them to get to market quickly, with shorter product life cycles, ahead of competitors. In addition to flexibility, organisations need to be innovative at both the production and organisational levels to be able to compete and survive in the marketplace. Organisations that fail to generate innovative solutions to the pressures and challenges they face will ultimately risk extinction. This highlights the critical role of knowledge management as it significantly influences and supports organisational innovation (Abu Shararar & Mohammed, 2019).

Knowledge management infrastructure is a critical foundation for organisational innovation, ensuring the effective flow and use of knowledge to support creativity and development processes. The stronger these infrastructures are supported by technology and skilled human resources, the greater the organisation's ability to achieve sustainable innovation and maintain a sustainable competitive advantage (Dimayuga, 2024). This study examines the relationship between knowledge management infrastructure and organisational innovation in the Iraqi pharmaceutical industry.

Previous Studies and Hypothesis Development

Study by Dimayuga (2024): "Knowledge Management Infrastructure, Organizational Innovation, and Performance Among Primary Educational Institutions."

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between core knowledge management infrastructure, organisational innovation, and performance among primary educational institutions in Batangas. A quantitative descriptive approach was adopted using a questionnaire for data collection. The findings revealed that knowledge management infrastructure plays a significant role in supporting organisational innovation processes in primary educational institutions. Based on these findings, the first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: Knowledge management infrastructure has a statistically significant impact on organisational innovation in the pharmaceutical industry

Study by Bakhsh et al. (2024): "The Moderating Role of Organizational Innovation Culture in the Relationship Between Organizational Structure and Organizational Innovation."

The general framework of this study was to analyse the impact of different dimensions of organisational structure on organisational innovation, with a particular focus on the moderating role of an innovative organisational culture. The study was conducted in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Karachi, Pakistan by selecting a purposive sample of 400 employees working in these enterprises. A specialised questionnaire was distributed to gather their opinions and perspectives on the issue. The results showed that the study supported the relationship between organisational structure and organisational innovation. Based on this, the second hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H2: Organizational structure has a statistically significant impact on organisational innovation in the pharmaceutical industry

Study by Naveed et al. (2022): "Do Organizations Really Evolve? Examining the Critical Relationship Between Organizational Culture and Organizational Innovation Toward Organizational Effectiveness: The Central Role of Organizational Resistance."

This study examines the impact of organisational culture on organisational effectiveness through organisational innovation. A questionnaire was used as the primary data collection tool, targeting 280 employees in the banking sector in Pakistan. Based on the analysis results, it was found that organisational culture positively influences organisational effectiveness through organisational innovation. In light of this, the third hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H3: There is a statistically significant impact of organisational culture on organizational innovation in the pharmaceutical sector

Study by Hussein et al. (2023): "The Mediating Role of Perceived IT Orientation in the Relationship Between Human Capital and Organizational Innovation as a Learning Orientation Mediator: A Literature Review."

This study aims to identify the mediating role of perceived IT orientation in the relationship between human capital and organisational innovation. The research was conducted in an electrical and electronics manufacturing company in Baghdad with a sample of 262 employees who completed a questionnaire. The main findings indicate a significant relationship between human capital (HC) and organisational innovation (OI) through learning orientation dimensions, including shared vision, commitment to learning and openness. Based on this, the fourth hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Human capital has a statistically significant impact on organisational innovation in the pharmaceutical industry

Study by Azeem et al. (2021): "Enhancing Competitive Advantage Through Organizational Culture, Shared Knowledge, and Organizational Innovation."

This study examines the relationship between organisational culture, shared knowledge, organisational innovation and competitive advantage. The study collected data from 294 managers in the industrial sector and analysed it using PLS-SEM to validate the findings and test the proposed relationships. The results indicate that organisational culture, shared knowledge and organisational innovation play a positive role in enhancing competitive advantage. Based on this, the fifth hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H5: There is a statistically significant impact of shared knowledge on organizational innovation

Study by Yue & Johar (2024): "The Impact of Digital Infrastructure on Digital Organizational Innovation in China."

This study examines the impact of digital infrastructure on digital organisational innovation in China. The research was conducted among 384 employees and managers in key industries within the digital economy. The results show that both information infrastructure and innovation infrastructure have a positive and direct impact on digital organisational innovation in Chinese organisations. Based on this, the sixth hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H6: There is a statistically significant impact of technological physical infrastructure on organisational innovation

Methodology

Research Problem

The pharmaceutical and medical supplies industry in Iraq faces several challenges, the most important of which is the weak technical and physical infrastructure. This deficiency negatively affects the design of effective knowledge management systems, which in turn negatively affects organisational innovation. To address these issues, the following research questions are posed:

1. How do pharmaceutical companies implement basic knowledge management infrastructure requirements?
2. To what extent do pharmaceutical companies prioritise organisational innovation?
3. Does the implementation of knowledge infrastructure support organisational innovation?

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing organisational innovation in the Iraqi pharmaceutical sector. This main objective is further divided into the following sub-objectives:

1. To identify and diagnose the challenges that hinder the implementation of knowledge infrastructure and organisational innovation requirements.
2. To address these challenges based on both theoretical and practical aspects of the current study.

Research Methodology

The research used a descriptive-analytical methodology to assess the impact of knowledge management infrastructure on promoting organisational creativity.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of five different pharmaceutical companies in Iraq. The sample consists of 390 individuals working in these companies, selected through purposive sampling. The sample includes general managers, department managers, division managers, unit managers, senior experts, engineers and administrative staff with university degrees.

Data Collection Tools

A questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) was designed to collect data from the selected pharmaceutical companies. A total of 390 questionnaires were distributed to personnel in the Iraqi pharmaceutical industry. Table 1 shows the primary and secondary components of the questionnaire, along with the Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each dimension.

Data Analysis Tools

Following the distribution and collection of the surveys, the data was filtered and analysed using SPSS and Amos software. This analysis sought to examine the three main research variables: knowledge management infrastructure, organisational innovation, and to evaluate the proposed hypotheses. Several observations and recommendations were derived from the research.

Table 1. Questionnaire Components and Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients (to be inserted).

Main Variables	Sub-Dimensions	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Knowledge Management Infrastructure	Organizational Structure	5	0.83
	Organizational Culture	5	0.80
	Human Capital	5	0.89
	Shared Knowledge	5	0.92
	Physical Technological Infrastructure	5	0.89
Organizational Innovation	Innovation Speed	5	0.88

	Innovation Quality	5	0.90
--	--------------------	---	------

Theoretical Framework

Knowledge Management Infrastructure

Al-Saadi (2023) defines knowledge management infrastructure as the main pillar on which knowledge management rests and which helps to facilitate its processes. It consists of organisational structure, organisational culture, information technology infrastructure and human capital. It is composed of several dimensions, which are:

1. Organisational Structure

Organisational structure can be defined as the framework that organises individuals and units within an organisation, building trust, principles and commonly accepted foundations. This structure should encourage participation within the organisation and be flexible enough to achieve the efficiency required for its role (Joseph & Gaba, 2020; Al-Sabaawi & Mohammad, 2024).

2. Organisational Culture

Organisational culture refers to a set of beliefs, values and assumptions shared by the members of an organisation. These shared values influence the behaviour of organisational members, guiding their decisions and actions and thereby influencing the effectiveness of the organisation. At the same time, organisational members develop a shared set of ideas and beliefs about what is real, what is important, and how to respond to these factors (Meng & Berger, 2019: 2).

3. Human Capital

Human capital refers to the intellectual capital generated by a range of characteristics such as knowledge, skills, attitudes and relationships that are embodied in an individual's mind, body and behaviour (Vidotto & Ferenhof, 2017).

4. Shared Knowledge

Shared knowledge refers to the mutual understanding among the members of the organisation and includes a set of common knowledge, cumulative experiences related to knowledge, activities and principles that support communication and coordination within the organisation. It includes elements such as a unified language, individual knowledge domains, shared knowledge schemes, agreed standards, and experiences shared among individuals within the organisation (Al-Rawji, 2022).

5. Information Technology Infrastructure

The information technology infrastructure refers to the IT equipment, communication networks and data, as well as the necessary IT personnel to support the distribution of IT tools. The information technology infrastructure consists of three main components (Al-Saadi, 2023, p. 75).

Organizational Innovation

Demircioglu (2016) defines organisational innovation as the introduction of something new (an idea, product, service, technology, process or strategy) into an organisation. Ganter & Hecker (2013) view organizational innovation as "the implementation of a new organizational method in a firm's business practices, workplace organization, or external relations that has not been used previously in the firm and is the result of strategic decisions made by management". Organisational innovation consists of several dimensions, which are:

1. Innovation Speed

Innovation speed refers to an organisation's ability to reduce the time it takes to develop and market products or processes compared to its competitors. Therefore, innovation speed is seen as a team-based efficiency that enables the organisation to respond quickly to customer demands and gain a high market position, acting as a driver and achieving greater profits (Wang, et. al., 2018).

2. Innovation Quality

Innovation quality refers to the effectiveness of innovation processes and their end results. It is described as the extent to which an organisation can add value to its products or services in terms of features, cost, reliability and flexibility. This innovation characteristic helps organisations to outperform their competitors by improving quality management, enhancing responsiveness and increasing customer satisfaction (Thabit & Baraka, 2024; Hussein, et. al., 2021).

Results

Analysis of Knowledge Management Infrastructure

Table (2) shows the responses of the study sample from the Iraqi pharmaceutical industry regarding the knowledge management infrastructure. The participants reached a consensus of 79% on the overall dimensions of the knowledge management infrastructure, which is considered an acceptable rate, with a mean of 3.6476 and a response rate of 72.9%. The best dimension was the physical infrastructure for information technology, which achieved a rate of (90%). This suggests that participants consider the physical infrastructure for information technology to be a critical element, underlining the importance of technology in meeting the needs of the knowledge management infrastructure, thereby enabling the organisation to achieve the goals of both technological and organisational innovation in the broadest sense. The gap percentage was 27%, which is considered mild because the standard deviation is less than 1. This indicates a uniformity in the perspectives of the sample, with no significant divergence in ideas about the knowledge management infrastructure.

Table 2. The Comprehensive Index of Responses from the Study Sample Concerning the Aspects of the Knowledge Management Infrastructure

Response Scale for Knowledge Management Infrastructure Results					
	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation	Response Rate	Gap Percentage
Organizational Structure	0.72	3.391	0.988	0.678	0.321
Organizational Culture	0.71	3.384	0.999	0.676	0.323
Human Capital	0.79	3.682	0.897	0.736	0.263
Human Knowledge	0.83	3.774	0.875	0.754	0.245
Physical Infrastructure	0.90	4.007	0.801	0.801	0.198
Average	0.79	3.6476	0.912	0.729	0.270

The analysis of the results of organisational innovation reveals, as shown in Table 3, the feedback of employees in the Iraqi pharmaceutical sector on the facets of organisational innovation. The results showed a consensus with a remarkable 75% agreement, as evidenced by a mean of 3.5445 and a response rate of 70.89%. The dimension with the highest concordance rate was 'speed of innovation' at 78%. This underlines that the speed of innovation is seen as the primary and most critical component of organisational innovation within the study sample. The gap percentage was

29.11%, reflecting a minimal amount of discrepancy as the standard deviation is less than 1, demonstrating a uniformity in the sample's views and a limited diversity of views regarding the characteristics of organisational innovation.

Table 3. The Overall Index of Responses from the Research Sample on the Characteristics of Organizational Innovation

Response Scale for the Results of Organizational Innovation Dimensions					
	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation	Response Rate	Gap Percentage
Innovation Quality	0.72	3.458	0.988	0.6916	0.3084
Innovation Speed	0.78	3.631	0.865	0.7262	0.2738
Average	0.75	3.5445	0.9265	0.7089	0.2911

Hypothesis Testing

Figure 1 shows the correlation between the study variables, indicating that knowledge management infrastructure affects organisational innovation. The data presented in the figure will assist in the analysis of the study hypotheses, which will be elaborated in the following sections:

Figure 1. Structural Equation Model to Test the Relationships Between Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Organisational Innovation

Testing Hypothesis (H1): The Correlation Between Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Organizational Innovation

The results in Table (4) show a strong positive relationship between knowledge management infrastructure and organisational innovation through its estimated value of 0.66. The standard error is 0.063, which indicates the reliability of the results of the study. The correlation is statistically significant with a value of 10.476. The extremely low significance value of 0.000 indicates a strong relevance between the variables. The knowledge management infrastructure accounts for 44% of what differentiates organisational innovation, based on the explained variance of 0.44. The preliminary hypothesis can be confirmed by these results.

Table 4. The Correlation Between Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Organizational Innovation

Relationship		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Variance	
Knowledge Management Infrastructure	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.66	0.063	10.476	0.000	0.44

The data presented in the figure will facilitate the testing of the research hypotheses, as detailed in the following sections and illustrated in Table (5).

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model for Examining the Relationships Among the Dimensions of Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Organisational Innovation.

Testing Hypothesis (H2): The Correlation Between Organisational Structure and Organisational Innovation

Table (5) shows that the relationship between organisational structure and organisational creativity has a statistical value of 0.63, indicating its positive effect on creativity outcomes. The statistical measure (0.000) indicates a strong evidence of significance in the results. Organisational structure accounts for 40% of the changes in organisational innovation according to the tested variance ratio of 0.40. The research results support the acceptance of hypothesis 2.

Testing Hypothesis (H3): The Relationship Between Organizational Culture and Organizational Innovation

The research results show that organisational culture has a strong impact (0.60) on organisational creativity. The results show that organisational culture explains 36% of the variation in organisational innovation with a variance ratio of 0.36. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is confirmed.

Evaluating Hypothesis (H4): The Correlation Between Human Capital and Organisational Innovation

Organisational innovation shows a slightly positive relationship with human capital according to the calculated value of 0.58. Human capital accounts for 34% of what explains the differences in organisational innovation, based on the obtained variance ratio value of 0.34. Therefore, hypothesis 4 is confirmed.

Testing Hypothesis (H5): The Relationship Between Shared Knowledge and Organisational Innovation

Organisational creativity is significantly influenced by shared knowledge with a predicted value of 0.76. Shared knowledge explains 58% of all variation in organisational innovation based on the result of 0.58. Therefore, hypothesis 5 is confirmed.

Testing Hypothesis (H6): The Relationship Between the Physical Infrastructure of Information Technology and Organisational Innovation

Physical infrastructure in information technology proves to have a significant impact on organisational creativity with an estimated value of 0.67. The variance ratio is 0.45, indicating that this variable accounts for up to 45% of the variation in organisational innovation. By analysing these results, hypothesis 6 proves to be valid.

Table 5. Regression Analysis Results (Relationships Between Variables)

Relationship		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Variance	
Organizational Structure	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.63	0.067	0.1063	0.000	0.40
Organizational Culture	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.60	0.071	0.1183	0.000	0.36
Human Capital	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.58	0.073	0.1258	0.000	0.34
Shared Knowledge	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.76	0.061	0.0802	0.000	0.58
IT Physical Infrastructure	▼	Organizational Innovation	0.67	0.064	0.0955	0.000	0.45

Discussion

The relationship between organisational innovation and knowledge management infrastructure was the focus of research using field study data from the Iraqi pharmaceutical sector. Employees in this sector have recognised the vital role of knowledge management infrastructure in supporting organisational innovation, with 79% of respondents agreeing with this notion. In addition, the dimension 'physical infrastructure of information technology' stood out with a level of agreement of 90%, confirming the active role of technology in improving administrative and organisational processes and enhancing the capacity for innovation.

There was a 75% agreement rate for the analysis of organisational innovation, showing that employees fully recognise the importance of innovation for pharmaceutical organisations.

Organisations ranked 'speed of innovation' first among the innovation dimensions, with 78% of employees agreeing on its importance.

The results of hypothesis testing indicated that knowledge management infrastructure has robust positive effects on firm innovation. All of the study's hypotheses were accepted based on positive findings regarding the measured dimensions of knowledge management infrastructure, including organisational structure, organisational culture, human capital, shared knowledge and information technology infrastructure.

Conclusion

The results show that knowledge management infrastructure plays a crucial role in supporting organisational innovation, with the impact of different dimensions varying. Innovation can be enhanced by promoting knowledge sharing, investing in technology and restructuring organisational policies to support a more innovative environment. Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. It is essential to increase investment in this area in order to accelerate the innovation process and gain a competitive advantage.
2. Work to simplify administrative procedures and promote a culture of innovation through more flexible policies.
3. Develop mechanisms for sharing knowledge among employees, such as adopting knowledge management techniques or providing a collaborative working environment.
4. Improving quality requires further focus, such as supporting research and development and improving quality management systems.

References

- Abu Sharar, M., & Khaled, M. (2019). Knowledge management and its impact on organizational innovation: An applied study on Palestinian telecommunications companies. *Journal of Business and Management*, 21(1), 45-56.
- Al-Batayneh, M. T., & Al-Zoubi, M. O. (2016). The impact of knowledge management infrastructure availability on organizational learning: A field study in commercial banks in northern Jordan. *Arab Journal of Administration*, 36(2), 275-296.
- Al-Rawji, M. S. A. (2022). *The role of knowledge management infrastructure in enhancing organizational readiness: A survey study at Asiacell Mobile Communications Company in Iraq* (Unpublished master's thesis). College of Administration and Economics, University of Mosul, Iraq.
- Al-Saadi, A. M. J. (2023). *The impact of strategic intelligence on enhancing creative performance—knowledge management infrastructure as an interactive variable: An exploratory study of the views of a sample of employees at the Basra Governorate Bureau* (Unpublished master's thesis). Administrative Technical College/Basra, Southern Technical University, Iraq.
- Al-Sabaawi, A. R., & Mohammad, M. I. (2024). The impact of the quality of higher education in enhancing sustainable development indicators in Iraq: Kirkuk University as a model. *Journal of Education and Research*, 12(3), 45-62.
- Azeem, M., Ahmed, M., Haider, S., & Sajjad, M. (2021). Expanding competitive advantage through organizational culture, knowledge sharing and organizational innovation. *Technology in Society*, 66, 101635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101635>

- Bakhsh, M., Kamal, Z., Billoo, T., Salman, S., & Aziz, A. (2024). Moderating role of organizational innovative culture in the relationship between organizational structure and organizational innovation. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*, 5(1), 112-130.
- Demircioglu, M. A. (2016). Organizational innovation. In A. Farazmand (Ed.), *Global encyclopedia of public administration, public policy, and governance* (pp. 1-5). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_2486-1
- Dimayuga, M. M. (2024). Knowledge management infrastructure, organization innovation and performance among basic educational institutions. *International Journal of Open-Access, Interdisciplinary*, 3(1), 15-27.
- Ganter, A., & Hecker, A. (2013). Deciphering antecedents of organizational innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(5), 575-584. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.02.040>
- Hussein, B. A. (2021). Dimensions of green quality and its role in accounting investigation green marketing: A field study in the State Company for Electrical and Electronic Industries in Iraq. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 25(5), 1-12.
- Hussein, M. K., Al-Tekreeti, R. B. N., Hasan, M. F., & Flayyih, H. H. (2023). The moderate role of the perceived orientation of information technology in the relationship between human capital and organizational innovation mediating orientations to learning: Literature review. *Ishtar Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 4(1), 1-8.
- Joseph, J., & Gaba, V. (2020). Organizational structure, information processing, and decision-making: A retrospective and road map for research. *Academy of Management Annals*, 14(1), 267-302. <https://doi.org/10.5465/annals.2016.0124>
- Meng, J., & Berger, B. K. (2019). The impact of organizational culture and leadership performance on PR professionals' job satisfaction: Testing the joint mediating effects of engagement and trust. *Public Relations Review*, 45(1), 64-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2018.11.002>
- Naveed, R. T., Alhaidan, H., Al Halbusi, H., & Al-Swidi, A. K. (2022). Do organizations really evolve? The critical link between organizational culture and organizational innovation toward organizational effectiveness: Pivotal role of organizational resistance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(2), 100178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100178>
- Soomro, B. A., Mangi, S., & Shah, N. (2021). Strategic factors and significance of organizational innovation and organizational learning in organizational performance. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(2), 481-506. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-05-2020-0186>
- Thabit, M. Z. M., & Barakah, H. M. (2024). Organizational climate and its impact on organizational innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 46(3), 561-588.
- Vidotto, J. D. F., Ferenhof, H. A., Selig, P. M., & Bastos, R. C. (2017). A human capital measurement scale. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 18(2), 316-329. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-12-2016-0145>
- Wang, Z., Wang, N., Cao, J., & Ye, X. (2016). The impact of intellectual capital–knowledge management strategy fit on firm performance. *Management Decision*, 54(8), 1861-1885. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-10-2015-0461>
- Yue, X., & Johar, M. G. (2024). The impact of digital infrastructure on organizational digital innovation in China. *Journal of Infrastructure, Policy and Development*, 8(12), 7586. <https://doi.org/10.24294/jipd.v8i12.7586>

